

ARTICLE

Disability-Inclusion in Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) Programs of the Municipalities in Camarines Norte

Malyn Manalo-Asay ¹

¹ Camarines Norte State College, MBA

¹ malynasay@cnc.edu.ph

Citation

Manalo-Asay, M. (2024). Disability-inclusion in disaster risk reduction management (DRRM) programs of the municipalities in Camarines Norte. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Econometrics*, 1(1), 43–54.

Submitted: 25-Sep, 2024

Accepted: 26-Oct, 2024

Published: 13-Nov, 2025

Vol. 1, No. 1, 2024.

 10.62762/JTAE.2024.000000

***Corresponding author:**

Malyn Manalo-Asay ¹

malynasay@cnc.edu.ph

Copyright © 2024 by author(s) and Scientific Research Publishing Inc. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License (CC BY 4.0).

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Open Access

Abstract

The study determined the inclusion of disability related concerns on the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) programs of the municipalities in Camarines Norte. This research presented Twelve (12) Municipal DRRMO Profile, Disability Inclusive Policies in DRRM Plans, Disability Inclusive Practices in the Implementation of DRR Programs, Data on Disability Population, Accessibility Features in the Evacuation Centers, Availability of Disability-Inclusive Early Warning System, Training of responders on Disability-Inclusive DRR, Orientation of Barangay Officials and Families of Persons With Disabilities (PWDs) on Disability-Inclusive DRR, Problems and Issues in the Implementation of DIDRR Plan, and Facilitating Factors in the Implementation of DIDRR Plan. The findings show the majority of the respondents have insufficient knowledge about the need of PWDs; they are not yet ready to cater PWDs before, during and after disaster; The disability-inclusive policies in the areas of DRRM of the respondents are not comprehensive to assure PWDs are safe before, during and after disaster; majority of the Municipalities represented the PWD to DRR programs/activities; majority of the respondents have available disability data in their respective municipalities; majority of the respondents are not observing the BP. 344 or also known as Accessibility Law for PWD; most of the respondents do not have inclusive provisions of early warning system for all types of disability; not all the respondents undergo orientations and comprehensive trainings on handling different types of disability; and, the Barangay Officials and Families of PWDs in the different Municipalities were not properly oriented on Disability-Inclusive DRR. This study not only works for the end-result of answering the problems presented in this research, but also as a great source of additional knowledge which can be developed for the advancement of disability-inclusion disaster risk reduction management in general and for the enhancement of community disaster preparedness.

Keywords: Persons with Disability, Accessibility, Inclusive, Disaster Risk Reduction Management

Introduction

The Philippines is one of the top countries in the world at risk of climate-related natural disasters, such as typhoons, sea level rise, flooding and extreme temperature. The Philippine government enacted the Republic Act 10121: Philippines Disaster Risk Reduction & Management Act 2010 states “Vulnerable and Marginalized Groups are defined as those that face higher exposure to disaster risk and poverty including, but not limited to, women, children, elderly, differently-abled people, and ethnic minorities”.

According to Camarines Norte – Persons with Disability Affairs Office (CN-PDAO), 6, 172 is the total population of identified persons with disability in the Province. Large numbers of populations that will result a large number of casualties. This means that vulnerable groups, including persons with disabilities, must be included. It is important to plan together with persons with disabilities in preparing for disasters. Persons with disabilities are themselves the experts in identifying their needs. Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) concerns the whole community.

A significant number of disaster response problems affecting the lives of anyone. It is important to focus on how the Philippine government assists the needs for security not just for persons without disability but for everybody. Persons with disabilities, along with other vulnerable groups, have to be brought to the forefront in disaster risk reduction efforts to ensure an inclusive and comprehensive approach to reduce disaster vulnerabilities.

The community organization should also train and organize quick response volunteer teams to provide rescue as well as logistic and psychosocial support. For large scale community-based planning, long-term and sustainable programs should be developed in partnership with the local government and even private organizations to reduce poverty by providing affordable shelter, food, and water for resettled or relocated communities to reduce their disaster vulnerability.

This research determined the programs and interventions of respective MDRRMO's in the province regarding the inclusion of disability concerns in their disaster preparedness planning.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study analyzed the inclusion of disability related concerns on the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) plans and programs of the municipalities in Camarines Norte.

Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What are the existing disability-inclusive policies in the following pillars of DRRM:

- 1.1 Disaster prevention and mitigation;
- 1.2 Disaster preparedness;
- 1.3 Disaster response; and
- 1.4 Disaster rehabilitation and recovery?

2. What are the current disability-inclusive practices in the implementation of DRRM programs in terms of the following:

- 2.1 Inclusion of disability sector in DRR programs/activities;
- 2.2 Data on disability population;
- 2.3 Accessibility features in the evacuation centers;
- 2.4 Availability of disability-inclusive Early Warning System;
- 2.5 Training of responders on disability-inclusive DRR; and

2.6 Orientation of Barangay officials and families of PWDs on disability-inclusive Barangay DRR plans?

3. What are the problems and gaps in the implementation of disability-inclusive DRR plans in the municipalities of Camarines Norte?
4. What are the facilitating factors in the implementation of disability-inclusive DRR plans in the municipalities of Camarines Norte?
5. What are the recommended measures to implement a relevant Disability-inclusive DRR plans in the municipalities of Camarines Norte?.

Methodology

This study was conducted in the twelve Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction Management Offices of Camarines Norte and their profile. These are Municipality of Basud, Daet, Capalongga, Labo, Mercedes, Panganiban, Paracale, Vinzons, San Lorenzo, San Vicente, Santa Elena and Talisay. The respondents are the Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction Management Offices.

The questionnaire was constructed based on the specific sub-problems of the study. Moreover, it conducted key informant interviews, qualitative survey, and round table discussion on Municipal Disaster Risk Reductions Management Offices from the different Municipalities in Camarines Norte. The Total Enumeration will be used in determining the respondents and undergo validation from the expert to gather accurate and factual data.

Results and Discussion

This paper deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data on the Disability-Inclusion in Disaster Risk Reduction Management Program of the Municipalities in Camarines Norte. This research presents the Municipal DRRMO Profile, Disability Inclusive Policies in DRRM Plans, Disability Inclusive Practices in the Implementation of DRR Programs, Data on Disability Population, Accessibility Features in the Evacuation Centers, Availability of Disability-Inclusive Early Warning System, Training of responders on Disability-Inclusive DRR, Orientation of Barangay Officials and Families of PWDs on Disability-Inclusive DRR, Problems and Issues in the Implementation of DIDRR Plan, and Facilitating Factors in the Implementation of DIDRR Plan.

Disability-Inclusive Policies in DRRM Plans

The A1 table shows the reflection of existing disability-inclusive policies in areas of DRRM which are prevention and mitigation, preparedness, response and rehabilitation and recovery. The Municipalities of Daet, Mercedes and San Vicente have specific disability inclusive policies in DRRM Plans. The Municipality of Basud and Paracale has weak or unclear disability inclusive policies in DRRM Plans. Furthermore, the Municipality of Capalongga, Jose Panganiban, Labo and Santa Elena has none or no disability inclusive policies in DRRM Plans. The Municipality of Talisay has specific policies in preparedness and response, but in prevention & mitigation and rehabilitation & recovery has none or no disability inclusive policies. And, The Municipality of Vinzons has general provision in three (3) areas of DRRM except to rehabilitation & recovery which has no disability inclusive policies in DRRM Plans. It indicates that the disability-inclusive policies in the areas of DRRM of the respondents are not comprehensive to assure the PWDs are safe before, during and after disaster.

A1 REFLECTION OF EXISTING DISABILITY-INCLUSIVE POLICIES IN THE AREAS OF DRRM

MUNICIPALITY	PREVENTION & MITIGATION	PREPAREDNESS	RESPONSE	REHABILITATION & RECOVERY
Basud	Weak/ Unclear	Weak/ Unclear	Weak/ Unclear	None
Capalonga	None	None	None	None
Daet	Has Specific	Has Specific	Has Specific	Has Specific
Jose Panganiban	None	None	None	None
Labo	None	None	None	None
Mercedes	Has Specific	Has Specific	Has Specific	Has Specific
Paracale	Weak/ Unclear	Weak/ Unclear	Weak/ Unclear	Weak/ Unclear
San Lorenzo Ruiz	General	General	General	General
San Vicente	Has Specific	Has Specific	Has Specific	Has Specific
Sta. Elena	None	None	None	None
Talisay	None	Has Specific	Has Specific	None
Vinzons	General	General	General	None

Disability Inclusive Practices in the Implementation of DRR Programs

Table 3, shows the Disability Inclusive Practices in the Implementation of DRR Programs. The B1 table shows the inclusion of PWD sector in DRR programs/activities. Persons with Disabilities (PWDs) are Often, Sometimes and Seldom represented to DRR programs or activities.

MUNICIPALITY	Persons with Disabilities are:		
	Often represented to DRR programs/activities	Sometimes represented to DRR programs/activities	Seldom represented to DRR programs/activities
Basud	/		
Capalonga			/
Daet	/		
Jose Panganiban	/		
Labo		/	
Mercedes	/		
Paracale		/	
San Lorenzo Ruiz		/	
San Vicente		/	
Sta. Elena			/
Talisay		/	
Vinzons	/		

The Municipality of Basud, Daet, Jose Panganiban, Mercedes and Vinzons was often

represented to DRR programs/activities. The Municipalities of Labo, Paracale, San Vicente, Talisay and San Lorenzo was sometimes represented to DRR programs/activities. And, the Municipalities of Capalonga and Santa Elena was seldom represented to DRR programs/activities. On the other hand, the Municipalities may consider the idea of De Leon (2010), from the introduction of his book, affirmed that community-based development projects are participatory in nature. Finding shows, majority of the Municipalities represented the persons with disabilities (pwws) to DRR programs/activities.

Data on Disability Population

Table 4 shows the Data on Disability Population. The B2 table shows the available disability data disaggregated by Age, Sex and Types of Disability.

MUNICIPALITY	Available disability data disaggregated:			
	By Age, Sex, and Types of Disability	Only by:		
		Age	Sex	Disability
Basud		/	/	
Capalonga	/			
Daet	/			
Jose Panganiban	/			
Labo	/			
Mercedes	/			
Paracale		/		
San Lorenzo Ruiz	/			
San Vicente	/			
Sta. Elena			/	/
Talisay	/			
Vinzons	/			

Note: According to the Municipality of San Vicente, its municipality’s disability data is disaggregated by age, sex, and types of disability. However, there are incomplete information/data in some barangays.

The Municipalities of Capalonga, Daet, Jose Panganiban, Labo, Mercedes, San Vicente, San Lorenzo Ruiz, Talisay and Vinzons are disaggregated by age, sex and types of disability. The Municipality of Basud was disaggregated by age and sex. The Municipality of Santa Elena was disaggregated by sex and types of disability. And, the Municipality of Paracale was disaggregated only in age. It implies that majority of the respondents has available disability data in their respective municipalities.

Accessibility Features in the Evacuation Centers

Table shows the Accessibility Features in the Evacuation Centers.

MUNICIPALITY	Universal design of ramps, toilets with available standby wheelchair	Presence of compliant accessibility features such as:		
		Ramps with Handrails	Toilet with Grab Bar	Standby Wheelchair
Basud	/			
Capalonga				
Daet	/	/	/	
Jose Panganiban				
Labo				
Mercedes		/	/	/
Paracale	/			
San Lorenzo Ruiz		/	/	
San Vicente		/	/	
Sta. Elena				
Talisay		/	/	/
Vinzons				

The Municipality of Basud, Daet and Paracale have the universal design of ramps, toilets with available standby wheelchair in the evacuation centers. The Municipalities of San Vicente and San Lorenzo Ruiz has ramps with handrails and toilet with grab bar. The Municipalities of Mercedes and Talisay has the three (3) accessibility features but not following the universal design. And, the Municipalities of Capalonga, Jose Panganiban, Labo, Santa Elena and Vinzons are not compliant in accessibility law.

Finding shows, that majority of the respondents are not observing the BP. 344 or also known as Accessibility Law for Persons with Disabilities (PWDs). The Local Government Units (LGUs) should aware about the Philippine Laws on Disability to avoid violations and compromises.

Availability of Disability-Inclusive Early Warning System

Table 6, shows the Availability of Disability-Inclusive Early Warning System.

MUNICIPALITY	Provision of Early Warning System for all types of disability	Provision of Early Warning System only for:			No Provision of Early Warning System for all types of disability
		Blind/Low Vision	Deaf/Hard of Hearing	Autism/Learning Disability	
Basud		/	/		
Capalonga	/				
Daet					/
Jose Panganiban					/
Labo		/	/		
Mercedes		/	/		
Paracale					/
San Lorenzo Ruiz		/	/		
San Vicente		/			
Sta. Elena					
Talisay		/	/		
Vinzons					

The B4 table shows the provisions of Early Warning System for all types of disability or only for: Blind/Low Vision, Deaf/Hard of Hearing, Autism/learning Disability and No provision of Early Warning System for PWDs. The Municipality of Capalonga was the only one which has the provisions of Early Warning System for all types of disability. The Municipalities of Basud, Labo, Mercedes, San Vicente, Talisay and San Lorenzo Ruiz has the provisions for persons with disability (pwds) which are Blind/Low Visions and Deaf/Hard of Hearing. It indicates that most of the respondents do not have inclusive provisions of early warning system for all types of disability.

Training of responders on Disability-Inclusive DRR

Table 7, shows the Training of responders on Disability-Inclusive DRR.

MUNICIPALITY	First responders were provided comprehensive training on handling different types of disability	First responders were provided orientation training on handling different types disability	First responders were not provided training on handling different types of disability
Basud		/	
Capalonga		/	
Daet	/	/	
Jose Panganiban			/
Labo			/
Mercedes	/		
Paracale			/
San Lorenzo Ruiz		/	
San Vicente	/		
Sta. Elena			/
Talisay			/
Vinzons	/		

The B5 table shows the first responders were provided comprehensive training, orientation or not even experience any training on handling different types of disability. The Municipalities of Mercedes, San Vicente and Vinzons are provided comprehensive training on handling different types of disability. The Municipalities of Basud, Capalonga and San Lorenzo Ruiz are provided orientation on handling different types of disability. Moreover, the Municipalities of Jose Panganiban, Labo, Paracale, Santa Elena and Talisay were not provided training on handling different types of disability. It implies that not all the respondents undergo orientations and comprehensive trainings on handling different types of disability.

Orientation of Barangay Officials and Families of PWDs on Disability-Inclusive DRR

Table 8, shows the Orientation of Barangay Officials and Families of PWDs on Disability-Inclusive DRR.

MUNICIPALITY	Barangay officials and families of PWDs were oriented on Disability-Inclusive DRR	Barangay officials and families of PWDs were not oriented on Disability-Inclusive DRR	Others (state if any)
Basud			Municipal officials were oriented on disability-inclusive DRR
Capalonga		/	Not implemented
Daet	/		
Jose Panganiban		/	
Labo		/	
Mercedes	/		
Paracale		/	
San Lorenzo Ruiz	/		
San Vicente	/		
Sta. Elena			Only 4 barangays out of 19 were oriented on disability-inclusive DRR
Talisay	/		
Vinzons		/	

The B6 table shows the Barangay Officials and Families of PWDs were oriented or not on Disability-Inclusive DRR. The Barangay Officials and Families of PWDs in the Municipalities of Daet, Mercedes, San Vicente, Talisay and San Lorenzo Ruiz were oriented on Disability-Inclusive DRR. The Barangay Officials and Families of PWDs in the Municipalities of Capalonga, Jose Panganiban, Labo, Paracale and Vinzons were not oriented on Disability-Inclusive DRR.

Furthermore, The Municipality of Basud stated that the Municipal officials were oriented on Disability-Inclusive DRR. And, the Municipality of Santa Elena stated only 4 Barangays out of 19 were oriented on Disability-Inclusive DRR. Finding shows, that the Barangay Officials and Families of PWDs in the different Municipalities were not properly oriented on Disability-Inclusive DRR.

Problems and Issues in the Implementation of DIDRR Plan

Table 9, shows the Problems and Issues in the Implementation of DIDRR Plan.

The C1 table shows the problems and issues in the implementation of DIDRR Plans in the twelve (12) Municipalities of Camarines Norte.

MUNICIPALITY	What are problems and issues in the implementation of DIDRR plans?
Basud	None
Capalonga	Not implemented

Daet	No budget for PWD Inclusive programs and activities
Jose Panganiban	DI-DRR Plan is not yet implemented
Labo	None, because the training on Disaster Preparedness and Emergency Response for PWD and senior citizen will only be conducted on the 2 nd week of October of the current year.
Mercedes	Geographical location and full cooperation of PWD
Paracale	Kakulangan ng proper orientation at training sa mga PWDs
San Lorenzo Ruiz	Persons with disabilities sector often felt that they were neglected on DRRM activities
San Vicente	Poor/Lack of participation of PWD during DIDRR planning Lack of awareness on DRR related issues No designated MDAO/ PWD Focal Person No additional EWS
Sta. Elena	On planning stage for the formulation of DIDRR Plan
Talisay	None
Vinzons	Very limited PPAs for persons with disabilities; weak representation in the council, only compliance

Finding shows that the problems and issues encountered by the MDDRMOs are about the budget, awareness and implementation. All of these, the main problem was the attitudinal barrier. These is about the initiatives of every leader in the Municipalities. The program would not run without a budget, without the participation of the community, and proper cooperation will lead to sustainability.

Facilitating Factors in the Implementation of DIDRR Plans

The table shows the Facilitating Factors in the Implementation of DIDRR Plans. The D1 table shows the facilitating factors that helped/assist in the successful implementation of DIDRR plans.

MUNICIPALITY	What are the facilitating factors that helped/assist in the successful implementation of DIDRR plans?
Basud	Designation MDAO and inclusion of MDAO representative in the MDRRMC and in meetings and planning
Daet	Cooperation of all sectors
Capalonga	None
Jose Panganiban	Support and commitment of local authorities to the initiative of DIDRR and also support in the advocacy of PWD orientation training for the actual participation of their MDRRMOs
Labo	None
Mercedes	Fund access thru LDRRMF and conducted of 1 st Paralympic DRR Skills
Paracale	Matulungan at maisama ang mga PWD sa plano, training at orientation para sa successful implementation of DIDRR Plans
San Lorenzo Ruiz	Coordination and participation of persons with disabilities sector

San Vicente	IEC and advocacy campaign to vulnerable sectors Prioritization of the vulnerable sectors during emergency response Compliance to accessibility of facilities
Sta. Elena	None
Talisay	We have organized PWD Group from Barangay and Municipal Level
Vinzons	It should be given attention and must be given emphasis in the next planning session. Integrate possible interventions for persons with disabilities. Mainstream Inclusive DIDRR.

It indicates that to make the implementation of DIDRR Plans become successful, the unity, cooperation, initiatives, and collaboration of leaders together with the PWDs are requirements to make these goal achieve. These findings support the results in the study of Ecija, et.al., (2024) that support from different stakeholders are necessary for the successful implementation of DRRM as it affect to the preparedness and competence of DRRM coordinators.

Conclusions

Based from the data gathered, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. Majority of the respondents has insufficient knowledge about the need of PWDs, the respondents are not yet ready to cater PWDs before, during and after disaster.
2. The disability-inclusive policies in the areas of DRRM of the respondents are not comprehensive to assure the PWDs are safe before, during and after disaster.
3. Majority of the Municipalities represented the PWDs to DRR programs/activities.
4. Majority of the respondents has available disability data in their respective municipalities.
5. Majority of the respondents are not observing the BP. 344 or also known as Accessibility Law for PWDs.
6. Most of the respondents do not have inclusive provisions of early warning system for all types of disability.
7. Not all the respondents undergo orientations and comprehensive trainings on handling different types of disability.
8. The Barangay Officials and Families of PWDs in the different Municipalities were not properly oriented on Disability-Inclusive DRR.

Recommendations

Based from the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are hereby suggested.

1. The Provincial Government Unit through Camarines Norte – Persons with Disability Office should conduct a round table discussion to the Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction Officer of different Municipalities together with the PDRRMOs. The MDRRMOs should have sufficient knowledge about the need of PWDs, and in order for them to cater PWDs before, during and after disaster.
2. The MDRRMOs should incorporate the disability-inclusive policies in the areas of DRRM to assure the safety and security of PWDs before, during and after disaster.
3. The MDRRMOs of every Municipalities should acknowledge the PWDs and represented to DRR programs/activities.
4. The MDRRMOs should have a comprehensive disability data available in their respective municipalities.
5. The government should punish those private or public establishments which are not following the BP. 344 or also known as Accessibility Law for PWDs.
6. The MDRRMOs should have inclusive provisions of early warning system for all types of disability.
7. The MDRRMOs should undergo orientations and comprehensive trainings on handling different types of disability.
8. The Barangay Officials and Families of PWDs in the different Municipalities should have proper orientation on Disability-Inclusive DRR.
9. The PDRRMOs and MDRRMOs of every Municipalities should have a comprehensive plan of action exclusive for PWDs and mainstream them in actual simulation activity before, during and after disaster.
10. The PDRRMOs and MDRRMOs of every Municipalities together with BDRRMC should have PWD Mapping in their respective area in order to locate the PWDs easily.
11. The PDRRMOs and MDRRMOs of every Municipalities together with BDRRMC should formulate accessible Early Warning System for PWDs. They should consider the different disabilities to address the specific needs of PWDs.
12. The LGUs should allocate budget for accessibility of evacuation area and observe the universal design

References

1. BMF, (2002). Biwako Millennium Framework for Action. Retrieved August 15, 2018, from <http://www.unescap.org>.
2. David Selby and Fumiyo Kagawa (2015). Disaster Risk Reduction in School Curricula: Case study from thirty countries. Retrieved August 15, 2018, from <http://www.unesco.org>
3. United Nation Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disability (2006). Key Frame
4. De Leon, Alwin B. (2010). Community-Based Development Project. Retrieved August 15, 2018, from <http://www.ndrrp.org.edu/>
5. Ecija, J, Abris, M & Sabejon, M (2024). Preparedness on disaster risk reduction management (DRRM) Measures, Competence and Challenges Faced by school DRRM Coordinators in Salcedo I District in the Division of Eastern Samar. *Psychology and Education: A Multi-Disciplinary Journal*.
6. Joel Rodstrom (2015). Strengthening Public Preparedness, Best practices and an analysis of efforts in Sweden. Division of Risk Management and Societal Safety. Lund University, Sweden. Retrieved August 15, 2018, from Report 5010, 1-32
7. Magunda, M.K. (2010). Communication System, Disaster Risk Reduction Strategy. Retrieved August 15, 2018, from <http://www.ndrrp.org.edu/>
8. Republic Act 10121, Act of (2010): Philippines Disaster Risk Reduction & Management. Grantham Research Institute on Climate Change and the Environment. Dated: May 27, 2010. Retrieved from LSE 2018
9. Steve Ronoh, et. al. (2015). Children with Disabilities and Disaster Risk Reduction: A Review. School of Environment and School of Counseling, Human Services and Social Work. The University of Auckland, New Zealand. Retrieved August 15, 2018 from www.ijdrs.com/www.springer.com/13753
10. Tabios, Guillermo Q. (2010), National Hydraulic Research Center, U.P. Diliman, Institute of Civil Engineering and Director. Retrieved August 15, 2018, from <http://www.ndrrp.org.edu/>
11. Works, Legislation and Policies on Disability. Retrieved August 15, 2018, from [hp://www.un.org/disabilities/](http://www.un.org/disabilities/)